

Computational analysis of 2E-1-(Anthracene-9-yl)-3-(4chlorophynyl) by density functional theory

R. Vijayakumar^a, V. Balachandran^b, B. Narayana^c, M. Karunanidhi^a

^aDepartment of Physics, Srimad Andavan Arts and Science College (Autonomous), Tiruchirappalli 620005, India

^bCentre for Research, Department of Physics, A.A. Government Arts College, Musiri 621211, India

^cDepartment of Studies in Chemistry, Mangalore University, Mangalagangotri 574 199, India

Abstract

Anthracene is a solid polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon consisting of three fused benzene rings derived from coal-tar or other residues of thermal pyrolysis. Anthracene is used in the artificial production of the red dye alizarin. It is also used in wood preservatives, insecticides, and coating materials. Anthracene is colorless but exhibits blue (400-500nm peak) fluorescence under ultraviolet light. The structure and several spectroscopic features along with reactivity parameters of anthracene-9-yl-3-(4chlorophynyl) have been studied using experimental techniques and tools derived from quantum chemical calculations. Structure optimization is followed by force field calculations based on density functional theory (DFT) at the B3LYP level of theory. Local reactivity descriptors such as Fukui functions and local softness have also been calculated to find out the reactive sites within the molecule. The geometry of the molecule was fully optimized, vibrational spectra were calculated and fundamental vibrations were assigned on the basis of potential energy distribution (PED) of the vibrational modes.

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